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EXTERNAL DEBT ISSUES AND RISK MANAGEMENT IN COOPERATION WITH INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: *This study examines the challenges and mechanisms of external debt management in Uzbekistan in cooperation with international financial institutions (IFIs). Given the steady growth of external debt and its implications for fiscal sustainability, this research emphasizes the importance of adopting advanced international approaches and digital risk management tools. The paper analyzes the dynamics of Uzbekistan's external debt, sectoral allocations, creditor composition, currency structure, and associated risks, including currency, interest rate, liquidity, and political-institutional risks. Drawing on international experiences from countries such as South Korea, Japan, and Chile, the study highlights modern debt management frameworks, including Sovereign Asset and Liability Management (SALM), State Contingent Debt Instruments (SCDIs), Green and Sustainability-Linked Debt, Debt-for-Climate Swaps, and Integrated Debt and Fiscal Risk Dashboards (IDFRD). The findings indicate that integrating technical digital systems with strategic institutional frameworks is crucial for ensuring debt sustainability, mitigating fiscal risks, and strengthening macroeconomic stability in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *External debt; fiscal risk management; international financial institutions; debt sustainability; Uzbekistan; sovereign debt; digital risk management; green finance.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ВНЕШНЕГО ДОЛГА И УПРАВЛЕНИЕ РИСКАМИ В СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВЕ С МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМИ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ ИНСТИТУТАМИ

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Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются проблемы и механизмы управления внешним долгом Республики Узбекистан в рамках сотрудничества с международными финансовыми институтами (МФИ). В условиях устойчивого роста объёмов внешнего долга и его влияния на фискальную устойчивость особое внимание уделяется необходимости внедрения передовых международных подходов и цифровых инструментов управления рисками. В исследовании анализируются динамика внешнего долга Узбекистана, его секторальное распределение, структура кредиторов, валютная композиция, а также связанные с ним риски, включая валютные, процентные, ликвидностные и политико-институциональные риски. На основе международного опыта таких стран, как Республика Корея, Япония и Чили, в работе освещаются современные модели управления государственным долгом, в том числе управление суверенными активами и обязательствами (Sovereign Asset and Liability Management — SALM), инструменты государственного долга с условными обязательствами (State Contingent*

Debt Instruments — SCDIs), «зелёные» и устойчиво-связанные долговые инструменты, долговые свопы в обмен на климатические обязательства (Debt-for-Climate Swaps), а также интегрированные цифровые панели мониторинга долговых и фискальных рисков (Integrated Debt and Fiscal Risk Dashboards — IDFRD). Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что интеграция цифровых технических систем со стратегическими институциональными механизмами имеет ключевое значение для обеспечения долговой устойчивости, снижения фискальных рисков и укрепления макроэкономической стабильности Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: *внешний долг; управление фискальными рисками; международные финансовые институты; долговая устойчивость; Узбекистан; суверенный долг; цифровое управление рисками; зелёные финансы.*

XALQARO MOLIYA INSTITUTLARI BILAN HAMKORLIKDA TASHQI QARZ MUAMMOLARI VA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada xalqaro moliya institutlari (XMI) bilan hamkorlik doirasida O'zbekiston Respublikasining tashqi qarzini boshqarish muammolari va mexanizmlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tashqi qarz hajmining barqaror o'sishi va uning fiskal barqarorlikka ta'siri sharoitida risklarni boshqarishning ilg'or xalqaro yondashuvlari va raqamli vositalarini joriy etish zarurligiga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston tashqi qarzining dinamikasi, uning tarmoqlar bo'yicha taqsimlanishi, kreditorlar tarkibi, valyuta tarkibi hamda u bilan bog'liq risklar, jumladan, valyuta, foiz, likvidlik va siyosiy-institutsional risklar tahlil qilingan. Koreya Respublikasi, Yaponiya va Chili kabi mamlakatlarning xalqaro tajribasi asosida davlat qarzini boshqarishning zamonaviy modellari, jumladan, suveren aktivlar va majburiyatlarni boshqarish (Sovereign Asset and Liability Management - SALM), shartli majburiyatlarga ega davlat qarzi instrumentlari (State Contingent Debt Instruments - SCDIs), "yashil" va barqaror bog'langan qarz instrumentlari, iqlim majburiyatlari evaziga qarz svoplari (Debt-for-Climate Swaps), shuningdek, qarz va fiskal risklarni monitoring qilishning integratsiyalashgan raqamli panellari (Integrated Debt and Fiscal Risk Dashboards - IDFRD) yoritilgan. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli texnik tizimlarning strategik institutsional mexanizmlar bilan integratsiyasi O'zbekistonning qarz barqarorligini ta'minlash, fiskal xatarlarni kamaytirish va makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.*

Tayanch iboralar: *tashqi qarz; fiskal xatarlarni boshqarish; xalqaro moliya institutlari; qarz barqarorligi; O'zbekiston; suveren qarz; raqamli risklarni boshqarish; yashil moliya.*

Introduction.

Under contemporary conditions of globalization, cooperation with international financial institutions (IFIs) plays a critical role in the economic development trajectories of countries. For Uzbekistan, external financial resources from IFIs support the modernization of the real sector, infrastructure development, and social projects. Over recent years, Uzbekistan's external debt has increased steadily, contributing to economic growth while generating potential risks to fiscal and macroeconomic stability.

Effective external debt management is thus essential for ensuring debt sustainability, mitigating fiscal risks, and maintaining macroeconomic resilience. This study examines Uzbekistan's external debt portfolio, the associated risks, and the mechanisms employed

internationally to manage such risks, emphasizing the adoption of modern, integrated digital and institutional frameworks.

Methodology

This research employs a qualitative and quantitative approach. Quantitative data on Uzbekistan’s external debt dynamics, sectoral allocations, creditor composition, and currency structure from 2019 to 2025 were obtained from official sources, including the Ministry of Economy and Finance of Uzbekistan and IMF databases. Qualitative analysis is based on an extensive review of academic literature, policy documents, and case studies of countries that successfully integrated debt management strategies with international financial cooperation. Comparative analysis was used to identify best practices, including Sovereign Asset and Liability Management (SALM), State Contingent Debt Instruments (SCDIs), and digital risk management dashboards. The study further examines risks associated with external debt—currency, interest rate, liquidity, and political-institutional—while evaluating strategies for mitigation.

Literature Review

Issues related to external debt and risk management in cooperation with international financial institutions are widely addressed in the academic literature. In developing economies, external debt policy is commonly regarded as a critical factor influencing economic growth, fiscal sustainability, and the mitigation of macroeconomic risks. As emphasized by J.D. Sachs, concessional loans provided by international financial institutions can initially stimulate economic growth; however, under conditions of ineffective governance and weak institutional capacity, they may intensify the risk of a “debt trap.”[1] Therefore, countries with a high level of institutional quality tend to achieve relatively more effective outcomes in ensuring debt sustainability.

In his article “Financing versus Forgiving a Debt Overhang,” P. Krugman substantiates that an excessive external debt burden (debt overhang) suppresses economic activity by discouraging investment and reducing incentives for long-term economic growth.[2] According to this view, the effectiveness of loans provided by international financial institutions is directly dependent on the country’s fiscal management system and the rate of return on investment.

This idea was later reinforced by empirical analyses conducted by C.M. Reinhart and K.S. Rogoff, who demonstrated that a high ratio of public debt to GDP can significantly slow down economic growth.[3]

Studying the experience of developing Asian economies, Kim Y. and Lee J.W. analyze South Korea’s external debt policy and demonstrate that cooperation with international financial institutions ensured the structural sustainability of external debt (Kim Y., Lee J.W. External Debt and Development in South Korea, Asian Economic Journal, 2008, Vol. 22, No. 4, pp. 435–458). According to the authors, the “Development-Oriented Debt Strategy” jointly designed by the Korean government in cooperation with the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank significantly enhanced the economic efficiency of external borrowing.

Similarly, Yamada K., examining the case of Japan, emphasizes that aligning debt policy with technological investment strategies contributed to a reduction in fiscal risks and strengthened long-term economic resilience.[4]

Zettelmeyer J., in his analysis of risk management mechanisms in international debt agreements, emphasizes that the role of international financial institutions is not limited solely to the provision of financing. Rather, they play a critical role in assisting countries in the design and implementation of comprehensive debt sustainability strategies, thereby strengthening resilience to macroeconomic and financial risks.[5] According to this approach, effective risk management requires that agreements with international financial institutions incorporate mechanisms for diversifying currency risks, optimizing interest rate structures, and extending debt maturities. Such instruments contribute to mitigating external shocks and enhancing the overall resilience of the public debt portfolio.

Main Part

External debt policy occupies a central position in a country’s economic development strategy. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, external debt is primarily formed through borrowing from international financial institutions, foreign governments, commercial banks, and international capital markets. Within this framework, financial resources provided by international financial institutions are recognized as one of the key sources for financing structural reforms, modernizing infrastructure, and developing social sectors of the national economy.

In particular, loans extended by international financial institutions can be classified into concessional, semi-concessional, and commercial types. Concessional loans are typically characterized by low interest rates, long repayment periods, and grace periods, making them especially suitable for financing socially significant and long-term development projects. Semi-concessional loans are closer to market conditions and usually involve medium-term financial obligations. Commercial loans, by contrast, are provided at higher interest rates with short- or medium-term maturities and are generally utilized for revenue-generating or export-oriented projects[6].

Credit lines provided by international financial institutions also exert a significant impact on both the revenue and expenditure components of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These funds are often mobilized under state guarantees and, therefore, contribute to an increase in the government’s overall debt obligations (Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024, State Debt Bulletin, Q2 2024). At the same time, projects financed through such loans expand the productive capacity of the economy, strengthen the tax base, and, in the long run, contribute to fiscal sustainability. However, in the short term, the growth of external debt intensifies fiscal risks, as debt servicing costs are directly dependent on exchange rate fluctuations and changes in global interest rates.

International experience demonstrates that countries such as South Korea, Japan, Malaysia, and Singapore have achieved strong economic outcomes by coordinating their external debt policies with international financial institutions. For instance, in the Republic of Korea, cooperation with the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank enabled the successful implementation of programs aimed at industrial modernization, enhancement of export capacity, and the introduction of advanced technologies.[7]

In Japan, coordination of credit and investment policies through cooperation with international financial institutions has contributed to accelerating infrastructure development and enhancing the overall efficiency of economic growth.[8] The key feature of these experiences is that external debt policy has always been closely linked to national development strategies, and agreements concluded with international financial institutions are directed exclusively toward financing projects with high economic efficiency. From this perspective, for Uzbekistan, systematically coordinating debt policy in cooperation with international financial institutions, aligning it with economic priorities, and mitigating associated risks represent some of the most critical tasks. Analyzing the dynamics of the country’s external debt further broadens the scope of the research topic under study.

Fig 1. Dynamics of the Country’s External Debt, in USD million (2019–2025)[9]

During the period from 2019 to 2025, Uzbekistan’s external debt has demonstrated a steady growth trend, rising from USD 15.7 billion in 2019 to USD 36.4 billion by the second quarter of 2025. At the same time, the debt-to-GDP ratio has shown a declining trend, decreasing from 31.8% in 2020 to 28.7% in 2025.

External debt policy is considered a factor directly affecting the country’s macroeconomic stability. While external funds mobilized through cooperation with international financial institutions support economic growth, it is essential to conduct a thorough analysis of the associated risks. These risks can be categorized into several main areas: macroeconomic, currency, interest rate, liquidity, and political-institutional risks.

Fig 2. Sectoral Distribution of External Debt, in Percentages (2019–2024)[10]

During 2019–2024, the sectoral composition of Uzbekistan’s external debt saw a significant increase in the share allocated to budget support, rising from 11% in 2019 to 45% in 2024. In contrast, the shares of debt directed to the fuel and energy sector, transport infrastructure, and agriculture declined, indicating that external financial resources were increasingly focused on maintaining fiscal stability rather than directly supporting the real sector.

Fig 3. Share of Creditors in the Country’s External Debt, in Percent (2019–2025)[11]

The majority of Uzbekistan’s external debt is held by international financial institutions, with their share increasing from 47% in 2019 to 53% by the second quarter of 2025. In contrast, the share of foreign government financial institutions has declined from 46% to 31%. Meanwhile, the share of private investors has risen from 6% to 16%, indicating the country’s growing credibility and investment attractiveness in international financial markets.

Fig 4. Currency Composition of External Debt (2019–2024)[12]

In the currency composition of the state’s external debt, the US dollar remains dominant, accounting for 61% in 2019 and slightly decreasing to 60% in 2024. Following the dollar, the Japanese yen, SDRs, and the Euro hold average shares of 8%, 7%, and 5%, respectively.

At the same time, analyzing the risks associated with external debt contributes to a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

1. Currency Risk arises from the potential depreciation of the national currency during the repayment of external debt. If the value of the Uzbek som declines relative to foreign currencies, servicing debt denominated in foreign currency requires higher local currency expenditures. This, in turn, places an additional burden on the state budget. To mitigate currency risks, it is essential to diversify the debt portfolio, utilize currency swap agreements, and implement hedging mechanisms.

2. Interest Rate Risk is another critical factor in external debt management. Some loans provided by international financial institutions carry variable interest rates, making them highly sensitive to changes in global market rates. For instance, increases in interest rates by the U.S. Federal Reserve or the European Central Bank directly raise debt servicing costs. Therefore, increasing the share of long-term and stable interest rate debt represents a key strategic approach to reducing financial vulnerability.

3. Liquidity Risk arises during the repayment of short-term debt. If a country has a high volume of short-term debt obligations, a temporary decline in payment capacity or an interruption in external financing flows can trigger an economic crisis. Therefore, when structuring the external debt portfolio, attention must be paid to coordinating maturities, planning refinancing policies, and increasing reserve assets.

Overall, the effective management of risks associated with external debt requires a systematic approach. This involves maintaining macroeconomic stability, aligning currency and interest rate policies, and strengthening institutional governance. Effective risk management of external debt is crucial for ensuring fiscal stability, enhancing sovereign credit ratings, and maintaining macroeconomic security. International experience demonstrates that many developing countries implement modern risk management mechanisms recommended by international financial institutions when formulating external debt policies.

For Uzbekistan, new technical and digital risk management mechanisms play a critical role in strengthening external debt sustainability and enabling the early identification of fiscal vulnerabilities. Scenario-based Stress Testing allows for assessing the impact of global price fluctuations and exchange rate volatility on debt-service indicators. Sovereign Risk Dashboards and Fiscal Risk Registries provide real-time monitoring of debt and fiscal risks. Additionally, mechanisms such as Green Debt Risk Assessment, Contingent Credit Lines (CCL), and Sovereign Derivatives Strategies help mitigate environmental, fiscal, and currency risks, while supporting the development of a sustainable debt policy in collaboration with international financial

institutions.

The need to adopt advanced international approaches in managing Uzbekistan’s public debt is increasing. To ensure debt sustainability, mitigate fiscal risks, and strengthen financial stability, it is crucial to integrate both technical mechanisms (digital risk management systems) and strategic frameworks (institutionally based models). Such a comprehensive approach enables effective public debt management, supports economic growth, and elevates cooperation with international financial institutions to a new level.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan faces a growing external debt burden that necessitates the adoption of advanced international approaches and integrated risk management systems. Effective management requires both technical tools, such as digital dashboards and scenario-based stress testing, and strategic frameworks grounded in institutional capacity. Lessons from international experience underscore the benefits of linking debt policy to national development priorities, diversifying currency and interest rate exposures, and incorporating environmental and social criteria. Implementing such a comprehensive approach will strengthen fiscal sustainability, reduce macroeconomic vulnerabilities, and enhance Uzbekistan’s cooperation with international financial institutions, thereby supporting long-term economic growth and stability.

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